

Health risk assessment of natural background radiation in the soil collected Over Ground water and Non-Groundwater from Deccan Peninsular Region, Pune City, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract

The present work attempts to analyze natural background radiation (NBR) of soil and body voltage of dowser over groundwater (GW) veins and non-groundwater (NGW) from the perspective of radioactivity. There seems to be sparse information about natural radioactivity levels in the soil of Pune, Maharashtra, India. As part of this study, soil samples were collected and estimated the radionuclide concentration in soil using HPGe gamma detector, and recorded the body voltage of the dowser by VM 20cBio/Voltmeter. The result showed that the activity concentration values for ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K has average mean values of 11.81±0.5 Bqkg⁻¹, 14.84±1.1 Bqkg⁻¹, 229.81±7.6 Bqkg⁻¹ over GW and 11.13±0.5 Bqkg⁻¹, 14.36±1.1 Bqkg⁻¹, 170±6.7 Bqkg⁻¹ over NGW respectively. The mean values of the samples for Radium equivalent radioactivity R_{eq} total gamma absorbed dose, total annual effective dose rate (AED), gamma index (I_γ), outdoor hazard index (H_{ex}), indoor hazard index (H_{in}), and cancer risk were 49.5±2.8 Bqkg⁻¹, 23.6 nGyh⁻¹, 0.13 mSvyr⁻¹, 0.18, 0.13, 0.16 and 0.09 over GW and 32.9±2.2 Bqkg⁻¹, 20 nGyh⁻¹, 0.12 mSvyr⁻¹, 0.17, 0.12, 0.15 and 0.08 over NGW respectively, with the obtained values been below UNSCEAR safe limit values.

The positive correlation between body voltage of dowsers and R_{eq} ($R^2=0.83$), AED ($R^2=0.84$) indicates that the NBR level, its rate dose in the soil of GW is good fit curve as compared to NGW, therefore body voltage (109>67mV) of dowsers changes while searching

for GW locations. The calculated values of I_γ , H_{ex} , H_{in} , and cancer risk over GW and NGW soil remain the same, but its percentage difference (% diff.) of radiation hazard index over GW soil is 20~21% more than NGW which is significant for the population living in the study area. The results obtained from the study regions revealed that the natural radiation level in GW is slightly higher than the NGW regions. These regions are safe for human habitation and outdoor activities, agriculture, building, and industrial activities.

Keywords: Soil, Natural radioactivity, HPGe detector, GW vein and NGW, Body voltage

1.0. Introduction

All living organisms and non-living things are constantly exposed to ionizing radiation emitted by various sources, called as natural background radiation (NBR) (Karunakara et al., 2014; Yasshodara et al., 2012; Murugesan et al., 2016; Daulta et al. 2019; Belyaeva et al., 2021; Filgueira et al. 2020). According to the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR 1988), there are three significant sources of natural background radiation: extraterrestrial radiation (cosmic radiation), terrestrial radiation (primordial radionuclides such as ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , ^{235}U), and internal radiation (intakes of naturally-occurring radionuclides like ^{40}K and ^{87}Rb through inhalation and ingestion) (UNSCEAR, 1988; IAEA, 1990; Amanjeet, et al., 2017; Lamarsh, 1983). Natural environmental radioactivity and gamma radiation emitted by naturally occurring radioisotopes such as ^{40}K and ^{232}Th , ^{226}Ra and their decay products, which are present in soil, rock, water, granite, building materials, etc., constitute terrestrial background radiation. It is largely dependent on the local strata and rock composition and is randomly distributed in soil in different parts of the world (Sing et al., 2017; Sannappa et al. 2003; Ridvan et al., 2011; Ramola et al., 2008; Tzortzis et al., 2004; Chiozzi et al., 2002; UNSCEAR, 2000; Arafa, 2004). Since radionuclides are not evenly distributed, measuring natural radioactivity in soil provides information about natural sources of radioactivity. Knowing the distribution of these radionuclides in the environment is essential and also plays an important role in assessing health risks to human and radiation protection. Therefore the measurement of natural soil radioactivity is of great interest to many researchers

around the world, and national surveys have been conducted worldwide over the past two decades (Belyaeva et al. 2021).

As a result of the above discussion, determining natural radioactivity in the soil is imperative. This is because animals and humans are exposed to cosmic rays and naturally occurring radionuclides (Murugesan et al., 2016; Daulta et al., 2019; Belyaeva et al., 2021; Filgueiras et al., 2020). Long-term exposure to these naturally occurring radionuclides can cause various diseases in humans, including acute leukopenia, cataracts, and kidney cancer (Singh et al., 2014; Quarashi et al., 2014; Taskin et al., 2009) which mainly consist of ^{238}U series, ^{232}Th series, and ^{40}K (Wang et al., 2017), that are present in almost all types of soils and are a significant cause of natural radioactivity. Natural radiation data can be used for a variety of purposes, including mineral exploration, identification of technical uranium contamination, risk assessment, and tracking of other environmental processes (Belyaeva et al., 2019). Once information about the distribution of ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , ^{226}Ra , and ^{40}K radionuclide's in the soil becomes available, appropriate measures can be implemented to mitigate radiation exposure risks and potentially reduce the incidence of radiation-related illnesses. Therefore, quantification of NBR in the soil is of critical importance to assessing radiation exposure. The previous literature revealed that there are only a few regions in the world, such as Brazil, China, India, Austria, France, and Iran (Alencar et al., 2005; Wei et al., 2000; Rangaswamy., 2018), where high natural background radiation levels have been identified and it vary depending on the specific location of terrestrial radioactivity. Researchers from various countries have found that, whenever there is GW movement at a certain depth below earth's surface, unknown NBR is generated due to friction in opposite directions to its flow (Foulkes, 1971; Jishan, 1995; Kristel, 2016; Bachler, 2007). The effects created due to these strong radiation have been named with various names like: Black Streams (BS), Cancer Rays (CR), Negative Green Rays (NGR), Hartmann & Curry Lines (HCL), Leys Line (LL), Geopathic Stress (GS). However, the amount of information available scientifically about the nature of such radiation that arise

through the crust of the earth and affect the built environment and their detection is very sparse (Judy Jacka, 2004).

These unknown NBR are, however, a major factor in the development of diseases caused by GW (Dharmadhikari et al. 2019; Kharat , 2000; Pimplikar, 2010; Sorate, 2016). Dharmadhikari et al., 2019 revealed that when Dowser was searching for a groundwater spot, dowser felt an invisible form of radiation emanating from the ground. This form of radiation assisted dowsers to locate GW spot, although dowser had no idea what type of radiation it was. However, the aim of this paper is to investigation of the unknown natural background radiation levels of soil and body voltage of dowsers over GW veins and NGW in Pune region, Maharashtra, India from the perspective of natural radioactivity (^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K). Currently, it is unclear how much radioactivity is present in the soils and the body voltage of the dowser over GW vein and NGW in the study area. Soil samples were collected in the Pune region, estimated the radionuclide concentration in soil, and recorded the body voltage of the dowser. The results are compared with other measurements of radioactivity in the soils of different countries. Furthermore, R_{eq} , total gamma absorbed dose, AED, I_{γ} , H_{ex} , H_{in} , and cancer risk are calculated for soil and body voltage of dowsers over GW vein and NGW and compared with internationally recommended values.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study area and identification of GW location

The fieldwork was conducted at 22 locations (11 GW vein sites and 11 NGW sites) in the Pune region of West Indian Peninsula, India located at $18^{\circ}.31^1$ N, $73^{\circ}.55^1$ E (Figure1). The study area included residential, non-residential areas and inter-state highways situated in the valley of Mula and Mutha rivers on typical rugged deccan topography (popularly known as Deccan Traps) with elevation difference between the highest and lowest point being 30m. The mountain and hill ranges in the west, river basins with undulating topography at the center, and in the east highland plateaus with wider river basins mark the physical landscape of the region

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(Bhakare, 2010). The entire study region of Pune is mainly formed by two major parts of the Western Ghats and 2,000 m thick multiple layers of Deccan basalts formed 65 to 70 Ma (millions of years ago) during the Late Cretaceous period (Basavaiah et al., 2018). The occurrence of GW in limited quantity within hard rock terrains such as Deccan Traps in western India is well known. The main aquifer horizons are in vesicular, fractured and weathered basalts (Pawar, 1993). The inter-trap formations, such as red bole, also form aquifer horizons at places. The study area is dominated by zeolites as cavity fillings and veins in the basalt (Querol et al., 2002). The natural zeolites are characterized by water molecules in the pores and voids of the structure (Querol et al., 2002). This near-surface geophysical study was planned to understand the physical framework of basalts within which GW resides and moves.

Dharmadhikari (2019) in his work has given a description of the GW vein and NGW locations, soil samples were collected from these locations and the activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in the soils were measured using HPGe gamma detector. The methodology used to carry out this work involved dowsing for GW, a qualitative aspect that is well established since ancient times and has an accuracy of over 90% (Bird, 1993). In this study, L-rod dowsing was used to identify GW vein locations, GP3D water detector (Figure 2) made by Geophinex model GP-3D-WL were established at all locations to confirm the GW vein width and depth identified by dowsing (Dharmadhikari et al., 2011).

Figure 1: Map about locations in study area

Figure 2: Groundwater vein width and depth measurement using GP3D water detector

2.2 Sample collection, processing, analysis of samples and body voltage

A total of 22 surface soil samples (from 0 to 10 cm soil profile) were collected from Pune region (11 over GW and 11 from NGW locations) . The samples were processed following the standard procedure (EML, 1983; IAEA, 1989). After processing, they were

placed in 300 ml polypropylene containers and kept for 30 days to allow ^{226}Ra to come into equilibrium with its daughters taking care to prevent ^{222}Rn escaping from the container.

2.2.1 Analysis of samples

The activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in the samples were determined by the gamma spectrometry employing a 48% relative efficiency p-type low background HPGe detector with an energy resolution of 2.0 keV at 1.33 MeV (BEGE-5030, Canberra Industries Inc., USA). The spectrum was acquired and analyzed using a ^{32}K multichannel analyzer (Multiport Lynx MCA, CANBERRA) and GENIE-2000 software. The detector efficiency calibration was performed using the IAEA quality assurance reference materials: RG U, RG Th, RG K, and Soil-6 procured from IAEA. The details of the gamma spectrometer and efficiency calibration were presented in the previous publication (Karunakara et al., 2013; Mohan et al., 2018, 2019; Darwish et al., 2019, Sudeep et al., 2023). The samples were counted long enough to reduce the counting/statistical error. The ^{226}Ra activity was evaluated from the weighted mean of the activities of three photo peaks of ^{214}Bi (609.4, 1120.4, and 1764.7 keV). In the case of ^{232}Th , two photo peaks of ^{208}Tl (583.1 and 2614.5 keV) were used. Figure 3 depicts the different gamma line of various energies (photopeaks). The activity of ^{40}K was derived from the 1460.8 keV gamma line of this isotope. The minimum detection levels (MDL) for the above detecting system were 0.3 Bq kg^{-1} , 0.5 Bq kg^{-1} , and 1.3 Bq kg^{-1} , respectively for ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K for a counting time of 60,000 s.

GW

NGW

Figure 3: Energy peaks of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K of soil samples over GW and NGW

2.2.2 Body voltage

The body voltage measurement was carried out using VM 20cBio/Voltmeter made by LC electronic Germany. One end of the instrument was grounded in the earth and the other end, which has an electrode that was kept in the hand of the dowser. The body voltage was then measured, and it is shown in Figure 4.

2.3. Estimation of dose rate

2.3.1 Estimation of activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in soil

Activity concentrations of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K in soil were calculated using the formula (1) (Knoll, 1998). The radionuclide peaks are shown in Fig 2 for GW vein and NGW.

$$\text{Activity (Bq/kg)} = [(g/t_1) - (b/t_2) \pm \text{SD}] \times 100/\eta \times 100/a \times 1000/\text{wt} \text{ --- (1)}$$

where

g = Gross count (sample + background) in t_1 second

b = Background count of counter in t_2 second

SD = Standard deviation

η = Percent efficiency of HPGe system for a particular energy peak

a = Abundance factor of radionuclide for a particular energy peak

wt = dry weight of soil sample taken for analysis

2.3.2 Radium equivalent activity $Ra_{(eq)}$

Radium equivalent activity ($Ra_{(eq)}$) is the activity levels of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K which takes into account the radiological hazards associated with them. The distribution of radionuclides in the soil is not uniform. Therefore, the consistency of human exposure to radiation from ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K is defined as radium-equivalent activity and it is calculated as follows (Beretka and Mathew, 1985; UNSCEAR, 2000)

$$Ra_{eq} = R_{Ra} + 1.43 \times R_{Th} + 0.077 \times R_K \text{ -----(2)}$$

where Ra_{eq} (Bqkg⁻¹), R_{Ra} , R_{Th} and R_K are the activity (Bqkg⁻¹) of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K

2.3.3. Hazard Indices

a) Estimation of total gamma dose from soil radioactivity measurements

The activity concentrations values of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in soil and using a dose conversion factor of 0.462 nGyh⁻¹/Bqkg⁻¹ for ²²⁶Ra, 0.604 nGyh⁻¹/Bqkg⁻¹ for ²³²Th, and 0.0417 nGyh⁻¹/Bqkg⁻¹ for ⁴⁰K the total gamma dose rates were computed (Kocher and Sjoreen,1985; UNSCEAR, 2000; UNSCEAR, 2008; Sudeep et al., 2023).

$$D = 0.462 \times R_{Ra} + 0.604 \times R_{Th} + 0.0417 \times R_K \text{ -----(3)}$$

where D is total gamma radiation dose in nGyh⁻¹

R_{Ra} , R_{Th} , and R_K are the activity (Bqkg⁻¹) of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K respectively

A secular equilibrium between ²³⁸U and ²²⁶Ra was taken into account for the dose calculation. It should be noted that the ²²⁶Ra sub-series delivers around 98% of the external dose from the ²³⁸U series. Therefore, the dose estimation from the measurement of ²²⁶Ra is unaffected by any disequilibrium between ²³⁸U and ²²⁶Ra (UNSCEAR, 2000; Karunakara et al., 2013).

b) Annual Effective Dose (AED)

To estimate the annual effective dose rates, the conversion coefficient from absorbed dose in air to effective dose (0.7 Sv.Gy⁻¹), outdoor occupancy factor (0.2) and indoor occupancy factor (0.8) as prescribed in UNSCEAR (UNSCEAR, 2000 ,UNSCEAR,2008)are used. Therefore, the AED is calculated using the following equations (Eq. 4)

$$\text{Annual effective dose (mSv.y}^{-1}\text{)} = D(\text{nGy.h}^{-1}\text{)} \times T \times \text{OC} \times F \times 10^{-6} \text{ -----(4)}$$

where D = absorbed dose rate (nGyh⁻¹)

T = time (8760 hr/y), OC = the occupancy factor, F = conversion coefficient of absorbed dose to effective dose but for adult population it is 0.7 SvGy⁻¹

$$\text{Indoor effective dose (mSv.y}^{-1}\text{)} = D(\text{nGy.h}^{-1}\text{)} \times 8760 \text{hy}^{-1} \times 0.8 \times 0.7 \text{SvGy}^{-1} \times 10^{-6} \text{ ---- (4a)}$$

$$\text{Outdoor effective dose (mSv.y}^{-1}\text{)} = D(\text{nGy.h}^{-1}\text{)} \times 8760 \text{hy}^{-1} \times 0.2 \times 0.7 \text{SvGy}^{-1} \times 10^{-6} \text{ -----(4b)}$$

c) Gamma Index (I_γ)

This represents the overall radiation hazard due to the presence of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K in the soil. It was granted by the European Commission in 1999 and calculated using equation (5) (EC 1999).

$$I_{\gamma} = \left(\frac{A_{Ra}}{300}\right) + \left(\frac{A_{Th}}{200}\right) + \left(\frac{A_K}{3000}\right) \text{---(5)}$$

where I_γ is gamma index

A_{Ra}, A_{Th} and A_K are the activity of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K

d) Outdoor Hazard Index (H_{ex})

Soil is the main component of building materials that pose a risk of gamma radiation exposure. Assuming that 370 Bq kg⁻¹ from ²²⁶Ra, 259 Bq kg⁻¹ from ²³²Th, and 4810 Bq kg⁻¹ from ⁴⁰K all produce the same gamma dose rate. (Beretka and Mathew, 1985; Stoks and Young, 1992). We quantify this radiation exposure using equation (6).

$$H_{ex} = \left(\frac{A_{Ra}}{370}\right) + \left(\frac{A_{Th}}{259}\right) + \left(\frac{A_K}{4810}\right) \text{---(6)}$$

where H_{ex} is the outside hazard index and

A_{Ra}, A_{Th} and A_K are the activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K

e) Indoor Hazard Index (H_{in})

Radon and its daughter products are hazardous to the respiratory organs. The internal exposure to radon and its daughter isotopes is quantified by the Internal Hazard Index (H_{in}). It is calculated using the equation (7) (Beretka and Mathew, 1985).

$$H_{in} = \left(\frac{A_{Ra}}{185}\right) + \left(\frac{A_{Th}}{259}\right) + \left(\frac{A_K}{4810}\right) \text{---(7)}$$

where H_{in} is the inside hazard index and

A_{Ra}, A_{Th} and A_K are the activity of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K

The value of H_{ex} and H_{in} indices should be < 1.0 mSv y⁻¹ to avoid adversely affecting the population (Quindos Fernandez and Soto, 1987).

f) Cancer Risk

Outdoor cancer risk was calculated using equation (8) (Ramasamy et al.2013).

$$\text{Cancer Risk} = \text{AED} \times \text{DL} \times \text{RF} \text{ --- (8)}$$

AED is total annual effective dose equivalent(mSvy^{-1})

DL = is duration of life(65year)(Jain et al.1995)

RF is risk factor (ICRP60 uses values of 0.05Sv^{-1} for public.(ICRP,1991)

2.4 % Difference

The % difference formula determines the percentage difference between two numbers. The ratio of the difference in their values to their average, multiplied by 100, is the percent difference. When the difference between two values is divided by the average of the same values, a percentage difference calculation has occurred. The formula for percentage difference is given by

$$\text{Percentage difference} = (\text{Absolute difference} / \text{Average}) \times 100 \text{ ----- (9)}$$

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the results of the activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K , and $\text{Ra}_{(\text{eq})}$ radionuclide in soil samples. The world-wide average concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K is 32 Bqkg^{-1} , 45 Bqkg^{-1} , and 412 Bq kg^{-1} respectively (Table 4). According to the organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (1998), the value of 370 Bqkg^{-1} is the ideal value for exposure to the public as it is equal to 1.5 mSvyr^{-1} . A high value of the radium equilibrium index will cause public exposure to exceed the safe level and may lead to a stochastic effect and radiation-related issues.

The overall activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K are varied in the range of 7.9-17.4 Bq kg^{-1} with mean 11.81 Bq kg^{-1} , 9.4-21.1 Bq kg^{-1} with mean 14.84 Bqkg^{-1} and 147.8-330.4

Bq kg⁻¹ with mean 229.81 Bq kg⁻¹ respectively. Ra_(eq) activity is 37.4 - 64.7 Bq kg⁻¹ with a mean value of 49.97 Bq kg⁻¹.

The overall activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K is varied in the range of 8.7-14.3 Bq kg⁻¹ with mean 11.13 Bq kg⁻¹, 8.2 -20.7 Bq kg⁻¹ with mean 14.36 Bq kg⁻¹ and 107.5-228.1 Bq kg⁻¹ with mean 170.23 Bq kg⁻¹ respectively. Ra_(eq) activity is 23.70-42.82 Bq kg⁻¹ with a mean value of 32.86 Bq kg⁻¹.

The percentage difference between GW and NGW vein (% diff.) for ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K, and Ra_(eq) activity is 5.8-39.5% with a mean value of 19.5%, 4.8 -75.0% with a mean value of 28.3%, 3.9-92.4 % with mean value 30.6% and 11.6-72.8% with mean value 49.5% respectively. Among four (²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, ⁴⁰K, and Ra_(eq)) the activity concentration of ⁴⁰K and Ra_(eq) in soil samples of the GW site was found higher in comparison with ²²⁶Ra and ²³²Th than soil over the NGW site. Similarly % diff. of ⁴⁰K and Ra_(eq) in soil of the GW sites was found higher in comparisons with ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th than the NGW (Table 1).

The calculated total gamma absorbed dose and AED are shown in Table 2. Based on the data, the world average value of total gamma absorbed dose is 54 nGy h⁻¹ (UNSCEAR, 2000) (Table 4). A natural radionuclide in the soil contributes the majority of the dose rate absorbed in the air at a height of 1m. Therefore, the total gamma absorbed dose depends on the concentration of specific radionuclide activity. According to Al-Kaabi (2016), if the concentration of radionuclide in the soil sample area is high, the total gamma absorbed dose will also be high. It is observed that total gamma absorbed dose calculated from activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th, and ⁴⁰K ranges between 17.6 - 30 nGy h⁻¹ with a mean value of 23 nGy h⁻¹ over GW vein soil.

The corresponding indoor annual effective doses range from 0.086 - 0.15 mSv yr⁻¹ with a mean value of 0.11 mSv yr⁻¹, and outdoor annual effective dose range from 0.021-0.038 mSv yr⁻¹ with a mean value of 0.028 mSv yr⁻¹ for GW vein. Total AED on GW (indoor GW + outdoor GW) is seen 0.09-0.17 mSv yr⁻¹ with mean value 0.129 mSv yr⁻¹.

It is also observed that the total gamma absorbed dose calculated from activity concentration of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K ranges between 15-27 nGy h⁻¹ with a mean value of 21 nGy h⁻¹ over NGW soil. The corresponding indoor annual effective doses range from 0.07 - 0.13 mSv y⁻¹ with a mean value of 0.10 mSvyr⁻¹, and outdoor annual effective doses range from 0.019-0.033 mSv yr⁻¹ with a mean value of 0.021 mSvyr⁻¹ for NGW vein. Total AED on NGW (indoor NGW + outdoor NGW) is seen 0.08-0.15- mSvyr⁻¹ with mean value 0.11 mSvyr⁻¹. Total gamma dose, in GW soil are found slightly higher than NGW soil.

The same % diff. (~21%) is found in indoor and outdoor AED, total gamma absorbed dose found in GW and NGW vein soil samples.

While the worldwide average annual effective dose is approximately 0.5 mSvyr⁻¹ and the results for individual countries are generally varied in the range of 0.3 -0.6 mSvyr⁻¹ for indoor and outdoor (UNSCEAR, 2000; ICRP, 1993; Amanjeet, 2017). The results obtained for annual effective dose in the present study are within the range of the worldwide average value (Table 4) and remains same for GW and NGW.

The values calculated for the gamma index, outside and inside hazard index, and cancer risk of soil samples are summarized in Table 3. Since these values are lower than unity (EC, 1999), and % diff. is found 20~21 % (I_γ , H_{ex} , H_{in} , and cancer risk) which was almost same over GW vein and NGW soil samples.

Figure 4 shows the dowsers body voltage ranges between 67-109 mV with mean values 89.3 mV over GW and 5.8 -11.8 mV with mean values 9.6 mV over NGW locations. The dowsers' body voltages were found to be higher over GW locations as compared to NGW locations. Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows the good correlation between dowsers body voltage with $R_{\text{a(eq)}}$ ($R^2=0.83$), AED ($R^2=0.84$) over GW and found to be weak over NGW.

Figure 4 : Body voltage of dowser over GW and NGW locations

Figure 5: Correlation between $Ra_{(eq)}$ and Body Voltage of Dowser over GW and NGW

Figure 6: Correlation between Annual Effective Dose rate and Body Voltage of Dowser over GW and NGW

4. Conclusion

A comparison of natural radioactivity, % diff (^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K), $R_{a(\text{eq})}$, total gamma absorbed dose, AED, I_γ , H_{ex} , H_{in} , and cancer risk shows that ^{40}K , $R_{a(\text{eq})}$, and total gamma absorbed dose are slightly higher in soil over GW vein than soil over NGW vein. The radionuclide concentration values obtained in the present study is comparable with other parts

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of the world that have lower values of NORMs, UNSCEAR (2000). In Al-Kaabi (2016), if radionuclide's in soil sample are abundant, gamma absorbed dose will also be high, and the natural radionuclide's (^{40}K and several members of the ^{232}Th , ^{235}U , and ^{238}U natural radioactive decay chain) in soil are major sources of external radiation like gamma radiation. The positive correlation of body voltage of dowsers versus $R_{a(\text{eq})}$ ($R^2=0.83$), AED ($R^2=0.84$) indicates that the NBR level, its dose rate in the soil of GW is good fit as compared to NGW, therefore body voltage ($109>67\text{mV}$) of dowsers changes while searching for GW locations. This natural radiation can be easily identified by dowsing while searching GW locations. The subjectivity of dowsing can be removed by measuring changes in body voltage. Therefore, it can be concluded that the archaic method of using the human system to detect underground features such as ground water disturbs the body voltage. Also a person who occupies GW location for a long time will experience subtle changes in their body voltage. The simple methodology of detecting GW as suggested in this study may contribute to formulating norms at such locations (Dharmadhikari 2011). The calculated values of I_γ , H_{ex} , H_{in} , and cancer risk over GW and NGW soil remain the same, but percentage difference (% diff.) of radiation hazard index over GW soil is 20~21% more than NGW which is significant for the population living in the study area. This information can be used to represent baseline radiation levels for the Pune region. Moreover, this estimation will serve as a baseline for the detection of contamination, especially around the repository facility.

Table 1: Analytical result of the activity concentration and % diff. of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and Ra_{eq} of soil samples

Location No	^{226}Ra Activity (Bq/kg)		^{232}Th Activity (Bq/kg)		^{40}K Activity (Bq/kg)		$\text{Ra}_{(\text{eq})}$ Activity (Bq/kg)		% diff. ^{226}Ra Activity (GW & NGW)	% diff. ^{232}Th Activity (GW & NGW)	%diff. ^{40}K Activity (GW & NGW)	%diff. Ra_{eq} Activity (GW & NGW)
	GW	NGW	GW	NGW	GW	NGW	GW	NGW				
1	11.9±0.6	10.5±0.5	17.3±1.3	8.2±0.7	184.5±7.1	211.0±7.6	50.84±3.00	23.70±1.55	12.5	71.3	13.4	72.8
2	16.6±0.7	12.7±0.6	15.8±1.2	14.7±1.3	330.4±9.5	162.5±6.6	64.63±3.14	34.85±2.50	26.6	7.2	68.1	59.8
3	14.2±0.6	9.8±0.5	14.2±1.1	13.1±1.1	214.7±7.6	152.6±6.4	51.03±2.75	29.60±2.11	36.6	8.0	33.8	53.1
4	10.8±0.6	13.2±0.6	14.3±1.2	19.6±1.4	219.3±7.7	228.1±8.1	48.13±2.90	42.82±2.65	20.0	31.2	3.9	11.6
5	12.4±0.6	11.7±0.6	16.6±1.3	15.0±1.2	198.7±7.4	172.6±6.9	51.43±3.02	34.35±2.36	5.8	10.1	14.0	39.8
6	7.9±0.5	11.8±0.6	9.4±0.9	20.7±1.4	208.8±7.4	169.5±7.0	37.41±2.35	42.58±2.65	39.5	75.0	20.7	12.9
7	17.4±0.7	14.3±0.6	21.1±1.4	15.6±1.2	222.9±7.7	194.2±7.2	64.73±3.29	37.96±2.36	19.5	29.9	13.7	52.1
8	9.8±0.5	11.6±0.6	11.2±1.0	14.7±1.2	292.3±8.8	107.5±5.4	48.32±2.60	33.37±2.35	16.8	27.0	92.4	36.5
9	9.9±0.5	8.7±0.5	14.0±1.2	10.8±1.0	202.8±7.6	129.7±5.9	45.53±2.80	25.05±1.97	12.9	25.8	43.9	58.03
10	8.2±0.5	8.9±0.5	12.7±1.0	12.1±1.0	147.8±6.3	121.3±5.7	37.74±2.41	27.05±1.96	8.1	4.8	19.6	32.9
11	10.9±0.6	9.3±0.5	16.7±1.2	13.5±1.1	195.8±7.4	223.6±7.8	49.85±2.88	30.17±2.12	15.8	21.1	13.2	49.2
Range	7.9-17.4	8.7-14.3	9.4-21.1	8.2-20.7	147.8-330.4	107.5-228.1	37-4-64.7	23.7-42.8	5.8-39.5	4.8-75.0	3.9-92.4	11.6-72.8
Average	11.81±0.58	11.13±0.55	14.84±1.16	14.36±1.4	229.81±7.6	170.23±6.7	49.9731±2.83	32.8680±2.24	19.5	28.3	30.6	49.2
Median	10.9±0.6	11.6±0.6	14.3±1.2	14.7±1.2	208.8±7.6	169.5±6.9	49.85±2.8	33.37±2.3	16.8	25.8	19.6	49.2

GW: groundwater, NGW: non-groundwater, % diff.: percentage difference

Table 2: Gamma absorbed dose rate (GAD), annual effective dose (AED) and % diff. of GAD, AED of soil samples

Location No.	Total Gamma absorbed dose rate (D) (nGy h ⁻¹)		% diff. Total Gamma absorbed dose rate (D) (GW&NGW)	Annual effective dose (mSv.yr-1)						% diff. of Indoor effective dose (GW & NGW)	% diff. of Outdoor effective dose (GW & NGW)
				Indoor annual effective dose (mSv yr ⁻¹)		Outdoor annual effective dose (mSv yr ⁻¹)		Total AED on GW (Indoor GW + Outdoor GW)	Total AED on NGW (Indoor NGW+ Outdoor NGW)		
	GW	NGW		GW	NGW	GW	NGW				
1	23.64	18.60	23.8	0.115	0.091	0.028	0.022	0.130	0.102	23.3	24
2	30.99	21.52	36.0	0.152	0.105	0.038	0.026	0.171	0.118	36.5	37.5
3	24.09	18.80	24.6	0.118	0.092	0.029	0.023	0.132	0.103	24.7	23.0
4	22.77	27.44	18.6	0.111	0.134	0.027	0.033	0.125	0.151	18.7	20
5	24.04	21.66	10.4	0.117	0.106	0.029	0.026	0.132	0.119	9.8	10.9
6	18.03	25.02	32.4	0.088	0.122	0.022	0.030	0.099	0.138	32.3	30.7
7	30.07	24.12	21.9	0.147	0.118	0.036	0.029	0.165	0.133	21.8	21.5
8	23.48	18.72	22.5	0.115	0.091	0.028	0.022	0.129	0.103	23.3	24
9	21.48	15.95	29.5	0.105	0.078	0.026	0.019	0.118	0.088	29.5	31.1
10	17.62	16.47	6.7	0.086	0.080	0.021	0.020	0.097	0.090	7.2	4.8
11	23.28	21.77	6.7	0.114	0.106	0.028	0.026	0.128	0.120	7.2	7.4
Range	17.62-30.99	15.95-27.44	6.7-36.0	0.086-0.152	0.078-0.134	0.021-0.038	0.019-0.033	0.097-0.171	0.151-0.088	7.2-36.5	37.5
Average	23.59	20.19	21.9	0.11	0.10	0.28	0.025	0.12	0.11	21.3	21.3
Median	23.48	21.52	22.5	0.115	0.105	0.028	0.026	0.129	0.118	23.3	23

GW: groundwater, NGW: non-groundwater, % diff.: percentage difference

Table 3: Gamma index, outside and inside hazard index and cancer risk of soil samples

Location No	Gamma index		%diff of Gamma index (GW & NGW)	Outside hazard index		%diff of Outside Hazard Index(GW &NGW)	Inside hazard index		%diff of inside Hazard Index(GW&N GW)	Cancer risk		% diff of Cancer rick (GW& NGW)
	GW	NGW		GW	NGW		GW	NGW		GW	NGW	
1	0.187	0.146	24.7	0.137	0.103	27.7	0.169	0.132	24.6	0.094	0.074	23.8
2	0.244	0.170	35.9	0.174	0.124	33.1	0.219	0.159	31.8	0.123	0.085	36.5
3	0.189	0.149	24.1	0.137	0.108	23.5	0.176	0.135	26.2	0.095	0.074	24.8
4	0.180	0.218	18.7	0.129	0.158	19.9	0.159	0.194	19.9	0.090	0.109	19.0
5	0.190	0.171	10.5	0.138	0.125	10.2	0.172	0.157	9.3	0.095	0.086	9.9
6	0.142	0.199	32.9	0.101	0.147	37.0	0.122	0.178	37.5	0.071	0.099	32.9
7	0.237	0.190	22.1	0.174	0.139	22.6	0.221	0.177	21.9	0.119	0.096	21.3
8	0.186	0.148	22.8	0.130	0.110	16.6	0.156	0.141	10.1	0.093	0.074	22.7
9	0.170	0.126	29.8	0.122	0.092	28.6	0.149	0.115	25.6	0.085	0.063	29.7
10	0.140	0.130	7.0	0.101	0.095	5.9	0.124	0.120	3.3	0.070	0.065	7.4
11	0.185	0.173	6.7	0.134	0.123	8.4	0.164	0.148	9.7	0.092	0.086	6.7
Range	0.140-0.244	0.126-0.218	6.7-35.9	0.101-0.174	0.092-0.158	5.9-37.0	0.122-0.221	0.115-0.194	3.3-37.5	0.070-0.123	0.109	6.7-36.5
Average	0.18	0.16	21.3	0.13	0.12	21.2	0.16	0.15	19.9	0.09	0.08	21.3
Median	0.17	0.17	22.8	0.134	0.123	22.6	0.164	0.148	21.9	0.093	0.085	22.7

GW: groundwater, NGW: non-groundwater

Table 4: Comparison of primordial radionuclide concentration, gamma absorbed dose and annual effective dose

Region	Statistical parameter	Radionuclide concentration (Bq/kg)			Gamma absorbed dose estimated from radionuclide activity concentration	
		^{226}Ra	^{232}Th	^{40}K	Absorbed dose rate (nGyh ⁻¹)	Annual effective dose (mSvy ⁻¹)
Pune region (GW)	Range	7.9-17.4	9.4- 21.1	147.8-330.4	17.6-30.9	0.09-0.17
	Median	11.8	14.8	229.8	23.5	0.13
Pune region (NGW)	Range	8.7-14.3	8.2- 20.7	107.5-228.1	15.9-27.4	0.08-0.15
	Median	11.1	14.36	170.2	20.9	0.11
All India	Range	7-158.3	2.59-1520	38-766	-	-
	Median	29	64	400	70	0.08
Worldwide	Range	1.0-1000	0.05-360	2-2260	-	-
	Median	32	45	412	54	0.07

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